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“THE DIGITAL SHIFT: ENVISIONING THE FUTURE OF TEACHING AND LEARNING”

The year is 2025. Technology is everywhere. At home, at work, in schools. As we adjust and adapt to these constant changes brought by rapid technological advancements, we see shifts in how education works in the modern time. As a young teacher whose career just begun, I find it very interesting to think about how these innovations influence and will influence the teaching-learning process today and years from now. Letting my thoughts flow, these are my thoughts on some modern innovations in education I personally like and what more I expect in the future.

First is the flipped classroom approach and the integration of technology in the classroom. I am a huge fan of this approach both as a student and as a teacher myself. I was there to experience the shift first-hand. From the time of traditional classrooms to the modern ones we have today. Those days of sitting in the classroom, listening through hours and hours of lecture and getting information through reading textbooks and looking at charts. The time when computers were mainly for teachers to use. No internet, no youtube, not even group chats with classmates existed yet. Then comes the time when we started using search engines like google to study about topics in advance. Back then, we had to visit computer shops as using the internet on mobile phones was not a common thing at the time. I remember being very excited whenever we were to watch videos using projectors and speakers at school. When the pandemic started, I experienced the transition to completely remote learning. Online enrollment, online classes, online evaluation of grades, everything was online. When the pandemic finally ended, I experienced adjusting to the new hybrid schedules.

This is the modern classroom. Technology is now a part of everyday discussions and activities. Students have mobile phones, we have the internet, we can use other devices during class. In the flipped classroom approach, students can discover topics on their own in advance and have more time in school focused on other learning activities. Gone are the days when we can only get information from walls of text, and maybe occasional photos from books. There are many new ways to experience the lessons ourselves, which takes me to my next idea, virtual reality.

I believe that the best way to learn is through experience, and the modern innovation to make this more engaging? Virtual Reality. VR in education might be a little far-fetched as of now, especially since we are in a developing county. But how amazing would it be for learners to be able to experience lessons in a virtual space? Imagine learning about different biomes in Science and seeing them with your own eyes with the help of VR equipment? Impossible? I think not. VR technology is already used and being improved in the gaming

industry, even for games with multi-players. VR sets can even be used at home so why not use this opportunity for learning right?

Lastly, I want to talk about AI. Controversial, I know. One of, if not the most notable issues about technology in education in the present is the widespread use of Artificial Intelligence. In only a few years, AI technology has improved drastically and is now used for various tasks such as image and video generation or editing, virtual assistance, self-driving vehicles, social media, and many more. From the top of my head I can instantly name the well-known ones such as ChatGPT, Cici, Meta AI and Grok. This inevitably led to AI being a part of modern education as a means of generating text, photos and straight up answers to questions.

I will not sugarcoat it. I am a fan of the good benefits of AI, however, the issues surrounding it right now are undoubtedly terrible. It poses so many problems and threats in different ways. In the education sector, its use is causing students to overly rely on technology. Students can use generative AI to cheat and plagiarize which leads to problems regarding the evaluation of student work and performance. Are they getting their work done? Yes. Fast? Definitely yes. But are they practicing and applying what they must? No. They are letting AI do the work for them which defeats the purpose of these activities as practice to apply what they learn.

But what if we see it this way? AI as a learning assistant, like a tutor of sorts. I know this is already being developed, maybe already released though not yet well-known. An assistant that will not give students direct answers but will guide them and help them through the learning process. This is not to say that AI will someday replace actual teachers. This way, the students can prepare more effectively for lessons in advance, while the teacher can focus on facilitating learning in the classroom. Answering students concerns and questions, facilitating activities and teaching important values such as respect and discipline will still be on the teachers. The AI can help students be more efficient when they work and study alone.

Another fun thing I like to think of is using character AI for educational purposes. Imagine a character AI whom students can interact with based on people from our history, say, Dr. Jose Rizal for example. This can be a unique and fun way to learn more about our national hero and his great contributions to the history of our country. Character AI's already exist so why not use this in ways that can help students? Let us try to look at the positive side. The same way fire can burn and bring harm but also warmth and heat for us to use, AI can be a useful tool for advancing modern education.

I am calling it now. These will happen. Maybe soon, maybe later. With how fast new innovations get released, it will only be a matter of time. Of course, new problems will come with it, paired with existing ones such as the technological gap. Nevertheless, the world is changing and it is amazing to witness the ways education change along with it. One day, I will look back to my 23-year old self imagining these things while experiencing them real-time.